

Inside INFRA-ART

Newsletter #03 | September 2025

Welcome to the latest edition of the INFRA-ART newsletter!

In this issue, we're sharing exciting milestones — from new data collections and semantic interoperability developments to community engagement initiatives and our participation in international networks. Enjoy the reading!

~ the INFRA-ART Team

New data collections: volcanic rocks from Vesuvius

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library continues to grow with new datasets that enrich its value for heritage science research. Our latest addition features a fascinating **new set of volcanic rocks and minerals from the Vesuvius area** (Campania, southern Italy). Currently, XRF spectra are available, with additional data types to be added after we transition to our upgraded infrastructure. You can explore the collection [here](#).

Note: This is the final update on our current platform, with more exciting releases to come once the new environment is launched in late December this year.

Community feedback survey

To help guide future developments and ensure INFRA-ART continues to grow as a trusted, community-driven resource, we've launched a **user feedback survey**. Whether you've used the INFRA-ART Spectral Library for research, conservation, teaching, or exploration, your experience matters. This short survey, about 7–10 minutes, will help us improve the platform based on real community input. **Take the survey [here](#).**

RDA TIGER project update

We're excited to share the first key milestones in our **RDA TIGER-funded project FAIRMap4ART**, which aims to enhance the semantic interoperability of the existing datasets within the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. Over the past few months, our team has completed:

- ✦ A metadata gap report identifying key challenges in semantic interoperability, metadata granularity, and machine-actionability.
- ✦ A technical implementation plan outlining the roadmap for metadata mappings and schema development.

The FIDELIS Network brings together repositories that practice or aspire to practice **TRUST-inspiring and FAIR-enabling data practices**. It supports members through advocacy, knowledge exchange, and coordinated development — offering shared legal guidance, best practices, tools, and training, while promoting interoperability and alignment with the EOSC ecosystem.

Membership in the FIDELIS Network strengthens our commitment to continuous improvement and helps ensure that the INFRA-ART data service remains a trusted, **community-focused infrastructure**. We're excited to join this effort and align with a community working toward a more open, interoperable, and sustainable digital research ecosystem. You can learn more about the network [here](#).

FIDELIS Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories

Advancing transparency and TRUST

Joining a growing international effort, the INFRA-ART Spectral Library is now officially listed among the **repositories endorsing the TRUST Principles**. We have recently updated our [Data Governance policy](#) to reflect this alignment, strengthening transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability, and technology across our data service.

As part of this commitment, we contributed with a case study to the **RDA-WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group**, showcasing how TRUST has been embedded in our governance, workflows, and sustainability planning.

Highlights from our TRUST journey:

- ✓ **Transparency** – openly available governance and policy documents.
- ✓ **Responsibility** – clear stewardship roles.
- ✓ **User Focus** – responsive support, feedback channels, and educational outreach via our blog.

✔ **Sustainability** – ensured through adoption of open formats, and participation in trusted repository networks.

✔ **Technology** – ongoing development toward EOSC-compliant infrastructure and technical interoperability.

Find more on the TRUST Principles for digital repositories [here](#).

INFRA-ART at womENCourage™ 2025

We were proud to have the INFRA-ART Spectral Library showcased at the **12th ACM Celebration of Women in Computing: womENCourage™ 2025**, held in Braşov, Romania. This year's theme, "*Computer Science: A Catalyst for Educational Change*," focused on the transformative role of computer science in reshaping education. The event brought together students, researchers, and industry professionals to celebrate diversity in computing and explore how technology can drive innovation, education, and societal change.

Our poster, "**From FAIR Data to Educational Impact: A Digital Resource Advancing Heritage Science Research and Learning**," presented by Ioana Maria Corcea, showcased our recent efforts to advance the INFRA-ART Spectral Library into not only a FAIR-aligned data service, but also into an educational platform designed to provide open, specialized tools and resources for the heritage science community. Through initiatives like the **OPEN-SciART project**, INFRA-ART now offers educational materials on spectral data analysis, material characterization, and FAIR data practices, making it a valuable tool for students, researchers, and conservators alike. This milestone reflects our commitment to open science, equitable

access, and the creation of digital resources that bridge research and education. Learn more about the event [here](#).

womENCourage™ 2025 - 12th ACM Celebration of Women in Computing 17 - 19 September 2025 - Braşov, Romania

ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA
UNIVERSITY of IAŞI

Transilvania
University
of Braşov

BABEŞ-BOLYAI
UNIVERSITY

New listings for INFRA-ART

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library is now indexed in **OpenDOAR**, the leading global directory of open-access repositories. In addition, our data service has also been recently listed in the **Open Science Knowledge Hub**, Romania's national portal for open science resources. These inclusions strengthen our connection with both the international and regional open science communities, highlighting our commitment to transparent and accessible research data.

OPEN SCIENCE
KNOWLEDGE HUB

OpenDOAR

Stay connected

Stay updated and be part of the **INFRA-ART community**:

- [Subscribe to our newsletter](#) and share it with colleagues who may find it useful.
- Follow us on [LinkedIn](#) for real-time updates, news, and project developments.
- Explore our open resources on [Zenodo](#).

 | FIDELIS

 re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

 FAIRsharing.org
standards, databases, policies

 Jisc OpenDOAR